

Bristol Composites Institute

A Qualitative and Quantitative Benchmarking Review of Resin Infusion Simulation Software

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Background

- Industry is demanding larger, more complex parts, faster than ever before [4]
- Volumes of CF in production expected to increase over 10% per annum

- Current Prepreg Methods will struggle to match this demand
- High material costs, handling concerns, and long autoclave cycle times limit production
- Resin Infusion methods could potentially offer a solution, but are complex to design and require

Background

Simulations believed by many to be a solution, supplementing/reducing physical testing [5]

Current use limited by both issues plaguing the field (cost, complexity) and lack of trust/understanding by industry [6]

Outline

Qualitative

Identification

- 12 software identified and downselected

Commercial-Origin Solvers

- Produced by commercial organisations for industry use
- Typically High-Cost and Feature heavy
- Can be less efficient at specific tasks

Open-Source Solvers

- Developed by organisations voluntarily or through grants
- These solvers are released openly for people to use or alter
- Typically low-feature, low accuracy

Research-Origin Solvers

- Usually produced by universities for research purposes and expanded upon later for commercial applications
- Can be more efficient and utilitarian than commercial-origin, but also can lack features

Tangential Related Solvers

- Many software can simulate 'resin infusion' but aren't designed for it (e.g. injection moulding)
- This can be useful for organisations which already use it, but is not preferable for new use

Feature Analysis

Software/ Parameter	Forming Effects	Viscosity Evolution	Cure Integration	Defects	Control	With	3D Layer Flow	Gravity	Multi- Core
						Workarounds			
Key: ✓✓ Supported ✓ With Workarounds x Not Supported									
Solver-1	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓
Solver-2	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
Solver-3	✓	✓	x	✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Solver-4	✓	✓✓	✓	x	✓✓	✓	✓	x	x
Solver-5	✓	x	x	x	✓	✓	✓	x	x
Solver-6	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

Quantitative

Methodology

- 4 Solvers selected to test variability between each other
- Benchmarked against each other and experimental results
- Material Data gathered according to ISO standards (ISO 4410, 2555, 18280)
- Experimental setup used a 4k 0.5s camera time lapse of Infusion through clear Perspex mould
- Python scripts processed data, and compared resin time of arrival
 - Data was normalised and solvers compared to each other to minimise error

Quantitative

- Assessment of Accuracy, Variation, and Computational Cost
- 3 Test Cases Considered
 1. Flat Panel
 2. Flat Panel + Racetracking
 3. I-beam style Infusion + Racetracks

Test Case 1

- Flat Panel with balanced 0/90 and ± 45 plies
 - Resin reached gelation before full infusion could be reached

Test Case 1: Flat Panel

1.

2.

3.

4.

Test Case 2

- Much greater proportion infused, but 2 dry spots on lower section

Test Case 2: Flat Racetracks

1.

2.

3.

4.

Test Case 3

- More complicated shape to represent hypothetical I-beam
 - Invokes 2 curves, internal and external
 - Racetracks applied on one side

Test Case 3: Double Curved with Racetracks

1.

2.

3.

4.

Result Summary

- Solvers show interesting behaviour compared to one another. Global behaviour is consistent, allowing confident overall predictions
 - Overall mean error and variance between the four solvers stays relatively consistent for all three test cases
 - However, variance between the solvers increases for the second case, and reduces for the third case (though it remains higher than the first)
 - One hypothesis for this is different handling of the fabric-racetrack interactions, which are more prevalent in Test Case 2 than in Test Case 3
- Local differences are more apparent looking at the error point cloud maps.
 - This could make it difficult to rely on these for more advanced optimisations or active control methods
 - More testing on this should be done

Questions?

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